

A spatial framework to identify bright spots and structural gaps for the development of sociobiodiversity bioeconomy: evidence from the Brazilian Cerrado

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Abstract

This study develops a spatially explicit framework to assess the potential for a sociobiodiversity-based bioeconomy in the Brazilian Cerrado, Brazil's second-largest biome. The approach integrates three key dimensions: (i) production potential of non-timber forest products (NTFPs), based on long-term historical data and biodiversity indicators; (ii) availability of support infrastructure, including transport, energy, digital communication and water systems; and (iii) institutional capacity, measured through the presence and functional diversity of intermediary actors such as cooperatives, associations and NGOs. Using spatial analysis and clustering techniques across 1,434 municipalities, the study identifies distinct territorial patterns and reveals critical mismatches between ecological potential, infrastructure availability and governance capacity. Results show a strong north–south gradient in bioeconomy potential, with high biodiversity and production potential concentrated in the northern Cerrado, while infrastructure and institutional support are predominantly located in the south. The analysis identifies three territorial typologies: “bright spots”, where favorable conditions converge; “potential hubs”, where high ecological potential is constrained by limited infrastructure and actor support; and “underdeveloped areas”, which lack the necessary conditions for bioeconomy development. These findings highlight that biodiversity alone is insufficient to drive development, emphasizing the importance of integrating ecological, infrastructural and institutional dimensions. The study provides a scalable and transferable framework to support territorial planning, public policies and investment strategies aimed at fostering a sustainable and inclusive bioeconomy.

Key-words: Bioeconomy, Sociobiodiversity, NTFPs, Spatial analysis, Territorial planning, Sustainability, Infrastructure and Governance

1. Introduction

Several countries across the Global North and South have incorporated the concept of bioeconomy into policy strategies. While early approaches in the Global North focused primarily on replacing fossil-based resources and mitigating climate change, recent discussions in the Global South have increasingly emphasized bioeconomy as a pathway to integrate economic development, environmental conservation and social inclusion in alignment with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Grilli et al., 2024).

In Brazil, this perspective has evolved into the concept of sociobiodiversity bioeconomy, which connects biodiversity conservation with inclusive income generation and the valorization of traditional knowledge associated with native species (Lopes and Chiavari, 2022; MMA, 2009; Queiroz-Stein et al., 2024; Schwanke, 2019). The sustainable use of non-timber forest products (NTFPs) by indigenous peoples, family farmers and traditional communities represents a key component of this approach, supporting livelihoods, cultural identity and local economies (Noda and Noda, 2003).

Despite its potential, sociobiodiversity-based bioeconomy remains largely underdeveloped. Existing production systems are often characterized by low value addition, limited market integration and fragmented policy support (Carvalho Ribeiro et al., 2024). Although national strategies have emphasized the importance of strengthening sociobiodiversity value chains (MMA, 2009) and the National Bioeconomy Strategy (Decree n°. 12.044/2024), there is still a lack of production intelligence (Queiroz-Stein et al., 2024), territorial diagnostics and integrated analytical approaches capable of guiding investments and policy interventions (Abramovay, 2019; Araujo et al., 2024).

The Cerrado, Brazil's second-largest biome and a major agricultural frontier, exemplifies this challenge (Bolfe et al., 2020). While it hosts high biodiversity and a wide range of native species with economic potential, it also faces significant pressures, including land-use change, biodiversity loss and socio-economic inequalities (Saes et al., 2023). At the same time, the region presents a unique opportunity to develop a bioeconomy model that reconciles conservation with economic development, particularly through the sustainable use of NTFPs (Afonso et al., 2022; Carvalho Ribeiro et al., 2020; Guéneau et al., 2020; WWF, 2022).

Recent studies have highlighted the importance of intermediary actors, infrastructure and governance systems in enabling sociobiodiversity value chains (Bachi et al., 2023). Studies have identified intermediary actors in sociobiodiversity chains, along with the infrastructure to support production and commercialization (Araujo et al., 2024; Brondizio et al., 2021; Gross et al., 2022; Saes et al., 2023). While others have noted several promising ‘seed’ projects and initiatives across Cerrado to leverage native biodiversity economically (Bachi et al., 2023). However, these elements are often analyzed in isolation, and there is a lack of integrated, spatially explicit frameworks capable of capturing how ecological potential, infrastructure and institutional capacity interact across territories. Addressing this gap requires moving beyond isolated case studies toward scalable approaches that can identify where bioeconomy development is viable, where structural investments are needed and where foundational conditions are still absent.

This study proposes a spatially explicit analytical framework to assess the potential for sociobiodiversity-based bioeconomy development in the Cerrado. The framework integrates three key dimensions: (i) potential for traditional use of NTFPs, (ii) availability of support infrastructure and (iii) presence and functional diversity of intermediary actors. By combining these dimensions through spatial analysis and clustering techniques, the study identifies distinct territorial typologies, including areas with favorable conditions for immediate development, regions with high potential but limited support and areas lacking the necessary structural conditions.

By revealing spatial mismatches between ecological potential, infrastructure and institutional capacity, this study provides a basis for guiding territorial planning, informing public policies and supporting strategic investments aimed at building a sustainable and inclusive bioeconomy.

2. Methods

2.1 Data collection and analytical approach

This study adopts a spatially explicit approach to assess the potential for sociobiodiversity-based bioeconomy development in the Brazilian Cerrado by integrating ecological, infrastructural and institutional dimensions. The analysis was conducted across 1,434 municipalities, combining multiple datasets related to non-timber forest products (NTFPs), land use, intermediary actors and support infrastructure.

2.1.1 Potential traditional use of NTFPs

To estimate the potential for traditional use of NTFPs, we developed a composite indicator integrating historical production data, biodiversity-related variables and territorial characteristics associated with traditional resource use. Long-term official datasets on NTFP production were used to capture temporal variability, while complementary spatial layers representing native vegetation, protected areas and territories associated with traditional communities were incorporated to reflect ecological and socio-cultural conditions. All variables were standardized and integrated using spatial analytical techniques to generate a continuous surface representing the relative potential for traditional NTFP use across the territory (Bachi and Carvalho-Ribeiro, 2022). Additional analyses were conducted to explore the spatial relationships between NTFP potential and broader land-use dynamics and socioeconomic conditions (Supplementary material 1).

2.1.2 Intermediary actors

The presence and role of intermediary actors were assessed based on publicly available data on organizations involved in sociobiodiversity value chains, including cooperatives, associations, NGOs and institutional actors (J. Grabs et al., 2024). Two complementary dimensions were considered. Actor presence, reflecting the concentration of organizations within each municipality. As well as functional diversity, capturing the range of roles performed across production, market access, capacity building, advocacy and environmental conservation. A diversity-based approach was used to characterize the distribution of functions across territories, allowing the identification of areas with more complex and potentially resilient support networks (Grêt-Regamey et al., 2019). These dimensions were integrated to provide an overall assessment of institutional capacity supporting sociobiodiversity-based activities (SM2).

2.1.3 Infrastructure availability

To assess the spatial distribution of infrastructure, multiple indicators related to transport, energy, communication and water systems were integrated (Gross et al., 2022; Thacker et al., 2019). Infrastructure variables were derived from national-scale datasets and transformed into comparable metrics at the municipal level, capturing relative availability and density. A composite infrastructure index was developed to classify municipalities

according to their level of structural support, allowing the identification of regions with higher or lower capacity to sustain economic activities linked to sociobiodiversity (SM3).

2.2 Identification of territorial typologies

To identify patterns and group municipalities with similar characteristics, a clustering approach was applied combining the three main dimensions: NTFP potential, institutional capacity and infrastructure availability. The analysis allowed the identification of distinct territorial typologies, representing different levels of readiness for bioeconomy development. These typologies include areas with favorable conditions for immediate development, regions with high ecological potential but limited support and areas lacking the structural conditions required to enable bioeconomy activities (SM4).

3. Results

3.1 Spatial patterns of traditional NTFP potential

The spatial analysis reveals a pronounced north–south gradient in the potential for traditional NTFP use across the Cerrado (Figure 1). High-potential areas are predominantly concentrated in the northern portion of the biome, particularly in Maranhão, Piauí, Tocantins and Bahia, while southern regions exhibit substantially lower potential. Within-state heterogeneity is also evident, especially in Goiás and Minas Gerais, where northern subregions present higher potential compared to southern counterparts. The results further indicate that areas with higher NTFP potential tend to overlap with regions of greater social vulnerability (Fig.S4). This suggests that sociobiodiversity-based activities are closely associated with territories where livelihoods depend more directly on natural resources. At the same time, these areas show moderate associations with land-use change dynamics, particularly the expansion of pasture and, to a lesser extent, soybean cultivation. Overall, these patterns highlight a critical tension: regions with the highest ecological and production potential are also those facing greater socioeconomic vulnerability and land-use pressures.

Figure 1 – Areas with potential traditional NTFPs use in Cerrado.

3.2 Intermediary actors across Cerrado

The distribution of intermediary actors across the Cerrado is highly uneven and reveals significant structural limitations in the support network for sociobiodiversity chains (Fig.S7A). A large majority of municipalities (67%) present low actor presence, while only a small fraction shows high levels of actor concentration (Fig.S7B). Functional diversity is even more limited, with most municipalities characterized by a narrow range of roles, often concentrated in production support activities. Only 2% of municipalities can be classified as well-supported hubs, where both actor presence and functional diversity are high (Figure 2). These areas represent rare cases where multiple functions

such as production support, market access, capacity building and advocacy are combined, creating more resilient and capable systems.

Figure 2 – Actor richness and diversity matrix.

In contrast, 67% of municipalities fall into support-deficient areas, lacking both sufficient actor presence and functional diversity. Additionally, 31% are classified as specialized areas, where actor presence is relatively high but roles are limited, suggesting partial system development and missed opportunities for integration. No municipality was classified as Areas with Potential Gaps (Low Richness + High Diversity). These findings indicate that institutional capacity is a major limiting factor for the expansion of sociobiodiversity-based bioeconomy across the Cerrado.

3.3 Infrastructure availability

The spatial distribution of infrastructure across the Cerrado shows strong regional disparities and reinforces existing territorial inequalities (Figure 3). High levels of infrastructure availability are concentrated in a very small subset of municipalities (approximately 3%), primarily located in the southern and southeastern portions of the biome. These areas benefit from greater access to transport networks, energy systems and digital communication. In contrast, the vast majority of municipalities (93%) present low levels of infrastructure availability, particularly in northern and central regions (Fig.S8). This reveals a significant structural gap between areas with high ecological potential and those with the necessary conditions to support economic activities. The results show that infrastructure is not aligned with biodiversity potential, creating a spatial mismatch that limits the development of sociobiodiversity value chains.

Figure 3 – Support infrastructure availability in Cerrado.

3.4 Bright and dark spots of the sociobiodiversity bioeconomy

The integration of ecological, institutional and infrastructural dimensions reveals three distinct territorial typologies across the Cerrado. Approximately 12% of municipalities are classified as bright spots, where favorable conditions converge. These areas combine relatively high biodiversity potential, stronger actor networks and better infrastructure, making them suitable for immediate investment and scaling of bioeconomy initiatives. Another 8% correspond to potential hubs, characterized by high ecological potential but limited infrastructure and institutional support. These areas represent strategic opportunities for targeted investments, as improvements in infrastructure and actor networks could significantly enhance their development potential (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - Municipalities with a similar pattern of potential traditional NTFPs use, intermediary actor richness and diversity and infrastructure availability index, produced by cluster analysis.

The majority of the territory (80%) falls into underdeveloped areas, where all three dimensions are weak. These regions lack the foundational conditions required to support sociobiodiversity-based bioeconomy and would require long-term structural interventions. These results highlight a critical spatial mismatch: biodiversity potential is not sufficient to drive development. Instead, the convergence of ecological assets, infrastructure and institutional capacity determines the viability of bioeconomy pathways.

4. Discussion

4.1 Biodiversity traditional use and sociobiodiversity development

The results reveal a strong spatial concentration of sociobiodiversity potential in the northern Cerrado, reinforcing the role of this region as a key frontier for bioeconomy

development. These areas combine high biodiversity with active traditional use of NTFPs, indicating a strong link between ecological assets and local livelihoods.

However, this potential is not evenly distributed and is closely associated with regions of higher social vulnerability and increasing land-use pressures (Sano et al., 2019). This highlights a central paradox: the areas with the greatest potential for sociobiodiversity-based development are also those facing the most significant socio-economic and environmental challenges, aligned with findings from previous studies (Guéneau et al., 2020).

These findings suggest that bioeconomy strategies cannot rely solely on ecological potential (Mukul et al., 2010). Instead, they must integrate social and territorial conditions, particularly in regions undergoing rapid agricultural expansion, such as MATOPIBA (Polizel et al., 2021). In high-potential areas, particularly in the northern regions such as Maranhão, Piauí, Tocantins and Bahia (e.g., MATOPIBA), targeted policies that focus on sustainable resource management, incentives for conservation and community-based governance are crucial for ensuring the long-term sustainability of these regions (Bachi et al., 2023). Furthermore, sociobiodiversity initiatives in these regions could have dual benefits: supporting biodiversity conservation while also addressing social vulnerability through livelihood opportunities (Araujo et al., 2024). Without this integration, high-potential areas risk being converted to competing land uses before their sociobiodiversity value is realized.

4.2 Intermediary actors as enabling conditions

The uneven distribution of intermediary actors across the Cerrado reveals a critical structural constraint for sociobiodiversity development. Only a very small fraction of municipalities combines high actor presence with functional diversity, forming well-supported hubs capable of sustaining more complex and resilient value chains. This scenario was also found in Amazon (Brondizio et al., 2021). In contrast, the majority of municipalities lack either sufficient actors or diversity of roles, limiting their ability to access markets, diversify activities or respond to new opportunities.

This indicates that intermediary actors function as enabling conditions rather than complementary elements. Their presence and diversity directly influence whether sociobiodiversity potential can be converted into economic and social value. Areas with

such configuration likely benefit from a wider range of support mechanisms, from production assistance to market access and advocacy (Janina Grabs et al., 2024).

Moreover, regions with high actor presence but low functional diversity remain structurally incomplete, suggesting that diversification of roles beyond production support is essential for advancing value chains.

4.3 Infrastructure as a structural constraint

Infrastructure availability emerges as one of the most significant limiting factors for sociobiodiversity development in the Cerrado. The results show a clear spatial mismatch between ecological potential and infrastructure availability. While biodiversity and NTFP potential are concentrated in the north, infrastructure is predominantly located in the south and central regions. This disconnect limits the capacity of high-potential regions to access markets, coordinate actors and sustain economic activities.

Importantly, infrastructure is not neutral. Infrastructure supports sociobiodiversity development by enabling intermediary actor networks to operate effectively and by facilitating access to markets for NTFP products (Garrett et al., 2024). Thus, its distribution reflects historical development patterns focused on agriculture and extractive industries, reinforcing existing inequalities and shaping the geography of opportunities.

Roads are one of the main known factors of degradation in the Cerrado (Costa et al., 2019), therefore strategic road, energy and digital communication projects in these regions must be strategically planned to enhance sustainable sociobiodiversity development across the Cerrado. Without targeted investments, regions with high sociobiodiversity potential will remain structurally constrained, unable to translate ecological assets into development outcomes.

4.4 Territorial typologies and development pathways

The identification of three territorial typologies, namely bright spots, potential hubs and underdeveloped areas, provides a simplified but powerful representation of the spatial organization of sociobiodiversity bioeconomy in the Cerrado.

Bright spots represent rare areas (12% of the municipalities) where ecological potential, infrastructure and institutional capacity converge. Bright spots are well-equipped to support sociobiodiversity development due to their established infrastructure and robust network of intermediary actors (associations, cooperatives, NGOs). These territories are

positioned to lead bioeconomy development and serve as reference models for scaling successful practices.

Potential hubs, includes 8% of municipalities in the northern and southwestern regions of the Cerrado, highlight a different dynamic: regions with strong ecological potential but limited structural support. These areas represent the most strategic targets for investment, as relatively small improvements in infrastructure and institutional capacity could unlock significant development opportunities.

Underdeveloped areas, which comprise the majority of the territory, lack the foundational conditions required to support sociobiodiversity activities. In these regions, development pathways are likely to be slower and dependent on long-term structural transformations. On the other hand, their role is foundational, with a focus on laying the groundwork for future development.

Together, these typologies reinforce a central conclusion: the viability of sociobiodiversity bioeconomy depends on the convergence of ecological, infrastructural and institutional factors, rather than on biodiversity alone.

4.5 Implications for policy and future research

The findings highlight the need for differentiated strategies tailored to specific territorial conditions. Uniform policy approaches are unlikely to be effective given the high degree of spatial heterogeneity observed across the Cerrado.

From a policy perspective, priority should be given to strengthening intermediary actor networks, improving infrastructure in high-potential regions and promoting integrated land-use strategies that balance agricultural expansion and biodiversity conservation.

At the same time, the study has limitations. The analysis assumes relatively static conditions and relies on available datasets, which may not fully capture informal networks or rapidly changing dynamics. Future research could build on this framework by incorporating temporal dynamics, evaluating policy impacts and exploring additional dimensions such as cultural and behavioral factors.

5. Conclusion

This study provides a spatially explicit assessment of the sociobiodiversity bioeconomy potential in the Brazilian Cerrado by integrating three key dimensions: traditional NTFP

use, intermediary actor networks and infrastructure availability. The results reveal a structurally imbalanced landscape. While high biodiversity and production potential are concentrated in the northern Cerrado, infrastructure and institutional support are predominantly located in the south. This spatial mismatch limits the capacity of high-potential regions to convert ecological assets into sustainable economic opportunities. The identification of distinct territorial typologies, namely bright spots, potential hubs and underdeveloped areas, demonstrates that bioeconomy viability depends not only on biodiversity, but on the convergence of ecological, infrastructural and institutional conditions. In this context, infrastructure and intermediary actor networks emerge as critical enabling factors for sustainable development. By moving beyond isolated analyses of production, infrastructure or governance, this study advances a spatially integrated framework capable of identifying where bioeconomy development is feasible, where targeted investments are needed and where foundational conditions are still absent.

These findings highlight the need for differentiated, territorially targeted strategies that align conservation, economic development and social inclusion. Strengthening infrastructure and expanding institutional support in high-potential regions are key steps to unlocking the Cerrado's sociobiodiversity potential. Future research should explore temporal dynamics and policy effectiveness, particularly in rapidly changing regions. However, the framework presented here already provides a robust basis for guiding territorial planning, informing public policies and supporting strategic investments. Ultimately, fostering a sociobiodiversity-based bioeconomy in the Cerrado requires not only conserving biodiversity, but creating the conditions that allow it to generate value for local communities. Bridging these structural gaps is essential to building a resilient and inclusive development pathway.

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